

COMPUTER BASED LEARNING STRATEGIES IN ACQUISITION OF ELECTRICAL MACHINE MAINTENANCE SKILL DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC IN POLYTECHNICS IN RIVERS STATE

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Abstract

The study determined the computer based learning strategies in acquisition of electrical machine maintenance skill during COVID-19 pandemic in polytechnics in Rivers state. Two research questions guided the study while two null hypotheses formulated were tested at .05 level of significance. The study made use of descriptive survey design and was carried out in Rivers state. The respondents for the study were 47 comprising 37 lecturers and 10 instructors. There was no sampling because of manageable size of the population. A 13-item questionnaire was used as instrument for data collection. The Cronbach Alpha reliability method was used to determine the internal consistency of the questionnaire items and an overall reliability coefficient of .71 was obtained. The data collected were analyzed using mean, standard deviation and t-test statistics to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 probability level of significance. Results revealed that 13 computer based learning strategies were required for acquisition of electrical machine maintenance skill during COVID-19 pandemic in polytechnics in Rivers state. Hence, recommendations include that the findings of the study should be used for acquisition of electrical machine maintenance skill and the school management should organize workshops/seminars for lecturers and instructors on the use of computer based learning strategies in acquisition of electrical machine maintenance skill during COVID-19 pandemic in polytechnics in Rivers state.